

DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC ORGANIZATIONS: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

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Abstract

This article synthesizes evidence on the relationships among institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations, its implications for the development of future empirical research in more specific contexts. The review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines and employed an initial corpus of 2,623 bibliographic records drawn from 20 RIS files compiled from Google Scholar, Scopus, and ScienceDirect. After deduplication, 2,231 unique records remained. A staged screening process based on publication year, public organization context, digital governance relevance, and conceptual fit produced 134 metadata-based candidates, which were subsequently narrowed to 15 priority studies for full-text review. The synthesis indicates that institutional capacity is most operationalized through regulation, coordination, interoperability, civil servant competence, capability, and organizational adaptive capacity. Organizational culture functions as both an enabling and constraining condition, particularly through trust, digital leadership, collaboration, learning, and public values. Meanwhile, the effectiveness of digital governance is most consistently reflected in service quality, administrative efficiency, transparency, public trust, public value, and government effectiveness. Cross-study findings confirm that the effectiveness of digital governance cannot be understood as an automatic outcome of technology adoption; rather, it constitutes an organizational outcome shaped by the interaction between institutional readiness and organizational culture that supports change.

Keywords: digital governance, effectiveness, institutional capacity, organizational culture, public organizations

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation in public organizations has evolved beyond the mere digitization of administrative procedures toward digital governance that requires process integration, data interoperability, transparency, service responsiveness, and the more strategic use of information in decision-making. However, the existence of applications, platforms, and information systems does not automatically produce more effective governance. Dobrolyubova (2021) argues that government digital transformation should not be assessed solely based on the availability of electronic services, but must also be linked to effectiveness, efficiency, public value, stakeholder outcomes, as well as risks and costs. At the macro level, Androniceanu and Georgescu (2023) likewise demonstrate that the digitalization of public administration is positively associated with government effectiveness, although the strength of this relationship is strongly shaped by the maturity of digital transformation and the institutional capacity of each country.

This issue indicates that the effectiveness of digital governance cannot be understood merely as a technological matter. From the perspective of digital-era governance, Dunleavy et al. (2006) emphasize the importance of process reintegration, a more holistic orientation toward user needs, and digitalization that transforms the way organizations work, rather than simply converting manual procedures into electronic ones. In this context, the success of digital governance must be interpreted as the result of the interaction among institutional capability, organizational culture, and the quality of digital change implementation. From the perspective of institutional capacity, Suwarno and Wati (2020) show that the effectiveness of e-government at the provincial level depends on the combination of the action environment, public sector institutions, task networks, organization and human resources, as well as the presence of

a chief information officer. This argument is extended by Margariti et al. (2020), who conceptualize capacity as organizational interoperability maturity, namely the ability of public organizations to align processes, structures, and coordination across organizational boundaries. Institutional capacity in digital governance, therefore, should not be understood merely as the possession of resources, but also as the capability to coordinate action, maintain coherence, and manage change. From the perspective of organizational culture, recent literature shows that public sector digitalization is strongly influenced by trust, digital leadership, collaboration, learning, public values, and organizational responses to change. Kożuch and Sienkiewicz-Małyjurek (2025) position trust as a key driver of digital transformation in the public sector, while van Roekel et al. (2025) demonstrate that digital transformation leadership oriented toward public value is positively associated with leadership effectiveness, work engagement, and job satisfaction. At the same time, Weigl et al. (2024) show that user-centricity in e-government may conflict with accountability, pluralism, and citizen representation. This suggests that organizational culture does not operate as a passive background condition, but rather as a mechanism that can either enable or constrain digital change.

Although the relevant literature continues to expand, three main gaps remain. First, studies on institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance still tend to develop separately. Second, some studies focus on technology adoption without clearly distinguishing between digital system adoption and the effectiveness of digital governance as an organizational outcome. Third, evidence from public organization contexts, particularly local governments and developing countries, remains dispersed and has not been widely synthesized in an integrative manner. Accordingly, this article focuses on the relationship among institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations. This article addresses three research questions. First, how have studies over the last five years defined and operationalized institutional capacity, and how has this capacity influenced the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations? Second, what empirical evidence is available regarding the role of organizational culture in enabling or constraining the adoption and use of digital systems in the public sector? Third, what determinants and barriers are most frequently identified in relation to successful digital governance, and how can these findings inform the design of future empirical research? This article opens space for future empirical research to examine the relationship among institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in a more structured manner within specific public organization contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Institutional capacity in this study is understood as the ability of public organizations to coordinate rules, resources, relationships, and learning processes so that digital transformation can be implemented consistently. Baser and Morgan (2008) explain that organizational capacity is more appropriately viewed as the ability to commit and engage, to act, to build support, to adapt, and to maintain internal coherence. In the context of digital governance, this perspective helps explain why organizations equipped with similar technologies may nonetheless produce different outcomes, as also illustrated by Suwarno and Wati (2020). More recent literature has expanded the concept of capacity toward interoperability, capability, maturity, implementation capacity, and capacity building. Margariti et al. (2020) identify organizational interoperability maturity as an important indicator of a public organization's ability to align processes and operate across organizational boundaries. Mikalef et al. (2023) show that capability in public organizations can be understood as a combination of tangible, intangible, and human resources that influence performance. van Noordt and Tangi (2023) further argue that the capability to implement is more important than merely the capability to develop, because public value emerges from sustained use rather than from technology adoption alone.

Organizational culture is used in this article to explain the patterns of values, behavioral orientations, and work practices that enable or constrain digital change. Denison and Mishra (1995) emphasize the dimensions of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission as key determinants of organizational performance. The reviewed literature indicates that, in the public sector context, organizational culture is manifested through trust, leadership, collaboration, learning, public values, responsiveness, and resistance to change. Kożuch and Sienkiewicz-Małyjurek (2025), van Roekel et al. (2025), Weigl et al. (2024), Trein et al. (2025), Jabri and Ahmad (2025), and Busacca (2025) show that digital change depends heavily on the extent to which organizations are able to manage trust, foster digital leadership, build collective learning, and negotiate value conflicts. The effectiveness of digital governance in this article is positioned as an organizational outcome rather than as a synonym for digital system adoption. Dobrolyubova (2021) emphasizes that the outcomes of digital transformation must include effectiveness, efficiency, public value, stakeholder outcomes, costs, and risks. Androniceanu and Georgescu (2023) reinforce the macro-outcome dimension through government effectiveness, while Jabri and Ahmad (2025) show that,

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at the local government level, service quality, transparency, responsiveness, fairness, and trust are more substantive indicators than the mere availability of online services. These findings are consistent with the Digital-Era Governance perspective proposed by Dunleavy et al. (2006), which conceptualizes successful digital governance in terms of reintegration, needs-based holism, and digitization of processes. Accordingly, the effectiveness of digital governance can be understood as the degree to which public organizations succeed in integrating processes and data, organizing services more holistically around user needs, and digitizing core governmental processes in ways that improve service quality, administrative efficiency, transparency, trust, public value, and government effectiveness.

METHOD

This article employs a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) guided by PRISMA 2020. This design was selected because the purpose of the study is to synthesize conceptual and empirical evidence on the relationship between institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations. As a form of secondary research, this review was intended to identify, screen, and synthesize relevant literature systematically and transparently. Bibliographic data were obtained from reference exports through Publish or Perish using Google Scholar and Scopus, as well as from ScienceDirect/Elsevier. The collected bibliographic records included the title, author, year of publication, journal name, DOI, keywords, and abstract when available. The review corpus was restricted to the predetermined scope of discussion, namely studies addressing the relationship between institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations.

The study selection process began with 2,623 bibliographic records identified from Google Scholar, Scopus, and ScienceDirect/Elsevier. After the removal of 392 duplicate records, 2,231 unique records remained for screening. At this stage, 2,097 records were excluded because they did not meet the criteria related to publication year, public organization context, relevance to digital governance, or conceptual fit with the core constructs of the review. As a result, 134 articles proceeded to the eligibility assessment stage. After further examination, 119 articles were excluded because they did not sufficiently address the research questions or lacked adequate conceptual relevance. Finally, 15 studies were included in the qualitative synthesis. The next stage involved a full-text review of the 15 priority studies considered most capable of answering RQ1–RQ3. Of these, 13 studies were retained as the main core studies, while 2 studies were positioned as strong supporting studies because of their important theoretical contribution, although they did not function as the main empirical evidence. The final synthesis was conducted thematically by mapping:

- (1) the definition and operationalization of institutional capacity.
- (2) the organizational culture mechanisms that enable or constrain digital adoption and use.
- (3) the determinants and barriers most frequently associated with successful digital governance.

Through this procedure, the review aimed to produce an integrative understanding of how institutional readiness and organizational culture interact in shaping digital governance effectiveness in public organizations.

Gambar 1. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram of Study Selection

Note. Records were identified from Google Scholar, Scopus, and ScienceDirect/Elsevier (n = 2,623). After removing duplicate records (n = 392), 2,231 records were screened. A total of 134 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility, and 15 studies were included in the qualitative synthesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The thematic mapping of the 134 metadata-screened candidates indicates that the corpus is richest in the themes of digital governance effectiveness, performance, public value, barriers, implementation, and fragmentation. Leadership, collaborative learning, trust, and public values also appear quite prominently, whereas explicit references to institutional capacity are relatively less frequent, although they carry substantial theoretical weight. This pattern suggests that the relevant literature is more likely to explain outcomes and implementation barriers than to define institutional capacity in a literal or explicit manner.

Based on the in-depth screening process, 15 priority studies were selected for full-text review. Thirteen studies were positioned as the main core studies, while two studies (namely Kożuch and Sienkiewicz-Małyjurek (2025) and Nurullah et al. (2026)) were retained as strong supporting studies. Both remain important because they strengthen the theoretical logic concerning trust, digital transformation, and the mechanism of moderated relationships linking administrative efficiency, leadership, and organizational effectiveness.

The review of the research questions is presented as follows.

RQ1: How is institutional capacity defined and operationalized

The final synthesis shows that institutional capacity can no longer be understood narrowly as the mere existence of rules, structures, or resources. Suwarno and Wati (2020) demonstrate formal-institutional capacity through the dimensions of action environment, public sector institutions, task networks, organization and human resources, and the presence of a Chief Information Officer (CIO). In their study, the effectiveness of e-government was strongly

influenced by clarity of functions, regulatory support, civil servant capacity, and formal digital leadership. Margariti et al. (2020) extend this understanding through the concept of organizational interoperability maturity. From this perspective, the capacity of public organizations does not reside only at the internal organizational level, but also in their ability to align processes and coordinate across organizational boundaries. Efficient, cost-effective, and transparent digital public services require an adequate level of organizational interoperability.

At the level of capability, Mikalef et al. (2023) argue that AI capability consists of a combination of tangible, intangible, and human resources that influence organizational performance through process automation, cognitive insight, and cognitive engagement. Meanwhile, van Noordt and Tangi (2023) show that the capability to implement is more decisive for public value creation than the mere capability to develop. Their findings emphasize that institutional capacity in public organizations should be understood as implementation capacity and adaptive capacity, rather than simply as the ability to procure technology.

Martinez et al. (2025) show that local governance capacity for inclusive digital services includes user-friendly design, interoperability, awareness and engagement, political support, and data-driven decision-making. Busacca (2025) adds that capacity must be interpreted within a broader institutional context; institutional fragmentation can create a vicious circle that hinders service quality and increases the risk of exclusion. Overall, RQ1 indicates that institutional capacity in public organizations is most appropriately operationalized through regulation, coordination, interoperability, capability, capacity building, and the ability to manage organizational change.

RQ2: How organizational culture enables or constrains digital adoption

The review findings show that organizational culture rarely appears explicitly under the literal label of “organizational culture,” but its substance emerges very strongly through trust, digital leadership, collaboration, learning, public values, fairness, responsiveness, resistance to change, and organizational logics. Therefore, organizational culture in this synthesis is more appropriately understood as the value environment and behavioral patterns that shape acceptance or resistance toward digital change.

Kozuch and Sienkiewicz-Małyjurek (2025) position trust as a key driver of public-sector digital transformation. van Roekel et al. (2025) show that digital transformation leadership, oriented toward public value, operates through two dimensions, namely strategic and operational leadership. Weigl et al. (2024) demonstrate that user-centricity in e-government may conflict with accountability, pluralism, and citizen representation. This implies that digital change is always connected with value conflicts, legitimacy, and the relationship between public organizations and citizens.

Trein et al. (2025) show that collaborative innovation will fail when policy-oriented learning and power-oriented learning occur sequentially rather than in parallel. Jabri and Ahmad (2025) find that security, transparency, responsiveness, fairness, and trust form the basis for citizen acceptance of digital local government services, whereas cultural resistance and low digital literacy remain major barriers. Lemmettylä and Kinnunen (2025) and Busacca (2025) reinforce the broader organizational dimension, particularly leadership support, stakeholder involvement, organizational silos, and conflicting organizational logics. Thus, RQ2 shows that organizational culture constitutes an internal institutional condition that mediates the relationship between the direction of digital change and the actual behavior of civil servants as well as the quality of system implementation.

RQ3: Determinants and barriers of successful digital governance

Dobrolyubova (2021) provides the outcome foundation by emphasizing that digital governance research design should not stop at the availability of e-services. Outcomes must include effectiveness, efficiency, public value, stakeholder outcomes, costs, and risks. At the macro level, Androniceanu and Georgescu (2023) show that digitalization is positively associated with government effectiveness, although cross-country variation remains strongly influenced by the maturity of digital transformation and the institutional conditions of each country.

At the implementation level, Lemmettylä and Kinnunen (2025) show that the success of information systems in the public sector is shaped by six major domains, with key drivers including leadership support, stakeholder involvement, and usability, while the main barriers include user resistance, technical challenges, and organizational silos. Jabri and Ahmad (2025) add that service quality and trust are important determinants of digital service effectiveness at the local government level.

Busacca (2025) shows that institutional fragmentation and conflicting logics can hinder digitalization and produce uneven adoption. Martinez et al. (2025) underline capacity building, interoperability, engagement, political support, and data-driven solutions as prerequisites for inclusive digital services. Weigl et al. (2024) add a normative barrier in the form of conflict between user-centricity and public values, whereas Nurullah et al. (2026) position administrative efficiency as a mediator and transformational leadership as well as digital leadership as moderators.

Mikalef et al. (2023), van Noordt and Tangi (2023), and Trein et al. (2025) show that the type of capability, the quality of implementation, and parallel learning loops determine whether technology adoption can be translated into performance, public value, and successful collaborative innovation.

Overall, the most consistent determinants of successful digital governance are institutional implementation capacity, leadership support, trust, digital service quality, stakeholder involvement, interoperability, administrative efficiency, collaborative learning, and public value orientation. The most consistent barriers are institutional fragmentation, organizational silos, user resistance, technical and legal barriers, low digital literacy, cultural resistance, public value conflicts, and the inability of organizations to translate technology adoption into sustained use.

Cross-RQ Synthesis and Implications for Future Research

When RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3 are considered in an integrated manner, the overall synthesis pattern becomes clear. First, institutional capacity is not merely a matter of rules or resources, but also encompasses interoperability, capability, implementation capacity, maturity, capacity building, and the ability to manage organizational change. Second, organizational culture is more appropriately understood through trust, leadership, collaboration, learning, public values, responsiveness, resistance to change, and organizational logics. Third, the effectiveness of digital governance is most consistently reflected in organizational performance, public value creation, service quality, public trust, administrative efficiency, transparency, and government effectiveness.

These findings provide a strong basis for positioning institutional capacity and organizational culture as explanatory constructs, while placing the effectiveness of digital governance as an organizational outcome. From the perspective of Digital-Era Governance, Dunleavy et al. (2006) argue that the success of digital governance should not be measured by the number of online applications or services alone, but by the ability of public organizations to achieve reintegration, needs-based holism, and digitization of processes. In the context of this article, institutional capacity serves as a prerequisite for the reintegration of organizational processes, data, and functions, while organizational culture determines whether user needs are genuinely translated into more holistic services and whether core bureaucratic processes can be digitally transformed in a sustainable manner. Accordingly, service quality, transparency, administrative efficiency, trust, public value, and government effectiveness are more appropriately understood as manifestations of digital governance effectiveness than as mere indicators of technology adoption.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings of this review can be connected to the five core capabilities as a lens for institutional capacity, Denison as a framework for organizational culture, and Digital-Era Governance as an outcome framework. From a methodological perspective, future empirical research needs to draw clearer distinctions among digital system adoption, organizational explanatory constructs, and digital governance outcomes, so that the analysis does not fall into the error of equating the mere presence of applications with the successful realization of digital governance.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between institutional capacity, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of digital governance in public organizations is systemic in nature. Institutional capacity explains the organization's structural readiness to act, while organizational culture explains whether digital change can be internalized into work behavior, coordination, and organizational learning. Therefore, the effectiveness of digital governance cannot be understood solely in terms of the presence of applications, but rather as the product of a combination of institutional capabilities and a work culture that supports change.

Over the past five years, the literature has most frequently operationalized institutional capacity through regulation, civil servant competence, coordination, interoperability, capability, and adaptive capacity. Organizational culture, in turn, has been reflected through trust, digital leadership, collaboration, learning, public values, fairness, and resistance to change. Meanwhile, the effectiveness of digital governance has been most consistently reflected in organizational performance, public value creation, service quality, public trust, administrative efficiency, transparency, and government effectiveness. From the perspective of Digital-Era Governance, these findings confirm that the effectiveness of digital governance is more appropriately understood as the ability of public organizations to integrate processes and data, organize services more holistically around user needs, and digitize core governmental processes in a sustained manner.

This synthesis also reveals an important gap in the literature. Many studies have examined the digitalization of public organizations, but not all of them clearly distinguish between digital system adoption and the effectiveness of digital governance as an organizational outcome. As a result, academic discourse still tends to focus on the existence

of applications or technical implementation, without sufficiently addressing how institutional capacity and organizational culture operate simultaneously in shaping the success of digital transformation.

From a practical perspective, these findings suggest that public organizations need to strengthen implementation capacity, interoperability, cross-unit coordination, digital leadership, and a work culture that is more adaptive and collaborative. Digital transformation should not be managed merely as a technology project; rather, it should be treated as an organizational change process that affects structures, processes, values, and work behavior. At the same time, the findings of this review indicate that there remains considerable room for more contextualized and focused research to explain how institutional capacity and organizational culture interact in shaping digital governance outcomes in specific public organizations.

This review has several limitations. First, the initial corpus was derived from RIS files whose metadata were not fully uniform in terms of completeness. Second, the initial study selection was based on titles, metadata, and abstracts, meaning that in-depth full-text reading was conducted only for the 15 prioritized studies. These limitations do not invalidate the findings of the review; however, they should be acknowledged so that the results are interpreted in a proportionate manner.

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